

1 Manipulating grading strategy for the efficient harvesting of industrial poplar plantations

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21 Introduction

22

23 Poplar is a fast-growing short-lived tree species traditionally elected by farmers to grow a
24 supplemental wood crop capable of satisfying their need for tools and other materials. Poplar
25 developed as an industrial crop in the early 1900s with the purpose of supplying furniture factories
26 with a lightweight raw material, easy to work, impregnate and paint. These early industrial
27 plantations gained much success and are still very popular in many European countries (Heilmann
28 1999). Later on, at the end of the same century, a completely different cropping system gained much
29 favour in Europe and North America, this time designed to produce large amounts of low-grade
30 wood at even shorter intervals (Rosenqvist et al. 2000, Stanton et al. 2002). Rather than offering
31 high-value veneer logs to the furniture industries, these newer plantations produced pulpwood and
32 chips to support the demands of pulpmills, particle-board factories and bio-energy plants.

33

34 While both designed for the same species (poplar) and land type (farmland), these two cropping
35 systems followed two opposite concepts: the traditional system aimed at maximizing the value of
36 the final harvest, through relatively longer rotations, careful tending and accurate processing at the
37 time of harvest (Spinelli et al. 2011); the newer system aimed at minimizing cost through coppice
38 regeneration, minimum tending and simplified processing (whole-tree chipping) at the time of
39 harvest (Vanbeveren et al. 2017). Currently, neither seem to hold much potential for further
40 expansion, since the acreage occupied by the traditional system has been fluctuating around a
41 relatively stable level for decades, and the newer system is actually regressing (Helby et al. 2006).

42

43 A possible solution might be found in an intermediate system, where a relatively small management
44 cost is combined with a richer crop than just bulk biomass. This strategy has already been explored
45 in the past (FAO 2005, Spinelli et al. 2009) and is now being applied to the newest plantations
46 appeared in the last two decades. Placed between traditional poplar plantations and short-rotation
47 energy crops, these newest tree farms are designed to yield a mix of quality logs for high-value
48 products and low-grade tops for energy use. There are currently tens of thousands of hectares of

49 these plantations in Europe – especially in the Eastern regions (IPP 2019). The success of these
50 plantations hangs upon the very fine balance between product value and management cost. In
51 particular, harvesting represents a most critical step, because it accounts for a large share of the
52 overall management cost. At the same time, value recovery is only maximized through careful
53 harvesting and therefore sufficient resources must be invested in the harvesting process to avoid
54 product degrade. For that reason, harvesting managers must figure out how much they can simplify
55 the harvesting process before value losses exceed cost savings, and until what point they can lower
56 product specifications to increase the proportion of the most valuable product in the mix.

57
58 An example can be offered by the poplar plantations established in Slovakia by IKEA Industry, with
59 the main purpose of supplying their local factory with raw material for the production of an
60 innovative high-value light-weight board. In this case the higher-value target product consists of 4-
61 m logs with an 8-cm small-end diameter (SED) over bark. However, management considerations
62 suggest keeping rotation within the 5th year mark, and therefore these plantations yield relatively
63 small trees. Only a small proportion of these trees (ca. 20%) may offer a second 4-m log.
64 Nevertheless, as value recovery must be maximized, tops will be passed through the harvester head
65 in order to check whether they can make a second log or not. This operation takes valuable seconds
66 but results in the production of a second log only once in five attempts.

67
68 Therefore, the question arises about whether the additional revenue obtained from those extra logs
69 is large enough to offset their additional production cost. In particular, one may consider renouncing
70 the production of a second log and go for one log only, leaving the rest as an entire top. In that case,
71 forfeiting the additional revenue of a relatively small log would accrue the savings of a faster
72 processing and of larger tops, which are likely faster to load and handle when a large enough
73 forwarder is available.

74
75 Conversely, one may try and maximize log volume recovery by slightly relaxing the small end-
76 diameter specification and take it to 7 cm SED over bark. In that case, the proportion of second logs
77 would increase and more second-log manufacturing attempts would be successful.

78
79 The goal of this study was to determine the cost-benefit ratio of these two opposing strategies, one
80 aimed at decreasing process time (treatment A) and the other at increasing log volume recovery
81 (treatment B). The null hypothesis was that of no differences in time consumption and log yield
82 between the innovative strategy and the control (i.e. manufacturing as many logs as possible to an
83 8-cm SED specification).

84 85 **Materials and methods**

86
87 The two strategies were tested in February 2021, at two different sites located in Western Slovakia,
88 not far from the town of Veľké Leváre. In particular, Treatment A was tested in the plantation
89 established in Nivky (48° 31' 25.11" N; 17° 03' 25.21" E in WGS84), while Treatment B was tested
90 in a similar plantation established in Gajary (48° 29' 10.87" N; 16° 55' 25.52" in WGS84).

91
92 Both sites were characterized as “warm temperate, fully humid, with hot summer climate” (Cfb)
93 according to the Köppen-Geiger classification (Rubel et al 2017). The mean annual temperature was
94 11 °C in the 2014-2020 interval and the average annual precipitation was 742 mm. Both sites offered
95 Mollic Gleysol, with groundwater levels between 1.5 and 2.0 m from the surface. Soil texture was
96 loamy sand in Nivky, and sand in Gajary. Weather during all the test period was consistently cold

97 and wet, with occasional sleet spells: the soil was intermittently covered by a thin snow coat and
98 the air temperature varied from -5 to +8 C°.

99
100 Both plantations were 5-year-old poplar stands established at a square spacing of 3.0 m x 2.0 m with
101 the hybrid poplar (*Populus x euramericana* Dode (Guinier)). Clone 'AF16' was planted in Nivky, and
102 clone 'AF18' in Gajary (Heilig et al. 2021, Landgraf et al. 2020, Meyer et al. 2021).

103
104 Harvesting was conducted according to the mechanized cut-to-length method, using the classic
105 combination of a harvester and a forwarder. The same Rottne H8 harvester (125 kW, 10 t own
106 weight, head EGS 406 - <https://www.rottne.com/en/skogsmaskin/rottne-h-8/>) was deployed at
107 both sites, while different forwarders were used, and namely: a Sampo FR28 (140 kW, 13 t own
108 weight, 10 t payload capacity - [https://www.sampo-rosenlew.fi/forest-machines/fr28-
109 kuormatraktori-2/](https://www.sampo-rosenlew.fi/forest-machines/fr28-kuormatraktori-2/)) in Nivky and a Rottne F10 (125 kW, 14 t own weight, 10 t payload capacity -
110 <https://www.rottne.com/en/skogsmaskin/rottne-f-10b/>) in Gajary (Fig.1). Each machine had its
111 own operator, which was a qualified forestry professional with significant experience of his machine
112 and specific task. In Gajary, the same Rottne H8 harvester was operated by two separate drivers
113 (Operator X and Operator Y), who harvested half of the test blocks each. Operator replacement was
114 unplanned and depended on Operator X having to step down for personal reasons. Nevertheless,
115 that allowed testing operator effect on top of grading treatment effect, for harvester performance.
116 Of course, that was only tested in Gajary on 4 repetitions for each of the four combination
117 treatments (i.e. 2 grading treatments x 2 operators), and could be considered a probe rather a full-
118 size experiment.

119
120
121 *Insert FIGURE 1 – Here*

122
123
124 Before starting the test, all operators were informed about the purpose of the study and the
125 methods adopted, and all made their best efforts to cooperate towards the success of the trial. They
126 were all given at least one full day of practice outside the marked experimental blocks in order to
127 familiarize with their specific tasks and settings, before engaging with the experiment proper. All
128 harvester head measuring systems were checked and calibrated on 20 trees before starting the trial.
129 Afterwards, calibration was checked on 2 trees at the beginning of each working day. Harvest
130 instructions were the following:

131
132 Treatment 0 – Control: manufacture as many logs as possible to an 8-cm SED specification (Nivky & Gajary)
133 Treatment A – Simplified: manufacture only one log to an 8-cm SED specification and drop the rest (Nivky)
134 Treatment B – Reduced: manufacture as many logs as possible to a 7-cm SED specification (Gajary)

135
136
137 Since the control was applied to both sites with the same harvester and operator, this study accrued
138 the collateral benefit of exploring the site and clone effect on the harvester used in its standard
139 operational mode (Treatment 0).

140
141 Essentially, the experimental design was:

142
143 Control vs. Simplified Treatment (i.e. 0 vs. A), in Nivky: 8 + 8 repetitions (blocks)
144 Control vs. Reduced Treatment (i.e. 0 vs. B), in Gajary: 8 + 8 repetitions (blocks)

145 Control Gajary vs. Control Nivky (i.e. 0 Gajary vs. 0 Nivky): 4 + 8 repetitions (blocks) – harvester only
146 Operator X vs. Operator Y * Control vs. Reduced Treatment, in Gajary: 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 repetitions
147 (blocks)

148
149 At each site, 16 experimental blocks were selected for the test. Each block included 5 rows (15 m)
150 and extended to a depth of 65 m, thus covering a rectangular area of approximately 0.10 ha, and
151 including between 160 and 180 trees. The idea was that each experimental block should require at
152 least 1 work hour to fell and process, and as much to extract to the roadside. Furthermore, the
153 amount of wood on each experimental block had to be large enough for at least two full forwarder
154 loads – one for the logs and the other for the biomass (i.e. tops and branches). The experimental
155 blocks were randomly assigned to the control and the treatment, half each. The beginning and the
156 end of each experimental block was clearly marked with high-visibility paint to prevent
157 misunderstanding. The circumference at breast height of all trees in every block was measured
158 manually with a measuring tape and then divided by Pi to get diameter at breast height (DBH), over
159 bark. Furthermore, researchers selected 6 trees of each clone at each site, for destructive sampling.
160 Selected trees covered the whole DBH distribution and were representative of the height and form
161 for similarly-sized trees of the same clone at that site. The height of each sample tree was measured
162 with a logger’s tape, while its weight was determined with a portable scale (accuracy = 1 g)
163 separately for the logs and the residual biomass. That allowed building a DBH-height curve and an
164 allometric equation for that site, which was used for estimating the mean height and the standing
165 dry mass on each individual block.

166
167 Dry mass estimates were later adjusted using ad-hoc correction factors obtained by matching the
168 total log and biomass estimates with the actual amounts taken to the certified weighbridge available
169 at the receiving factory, separately by site and treatment. Moisture content (i.e. water mass
170 fraction) was determined both at the time of destructive sampling and at delivery to the factory, so
171 as to match dry mass with dry mass. In both cases, moisture content was determined with the
172 gravimetric method, according to EN ISO 18134-2:2015. Mean moisture content at delivery was 57%
173 (standard deviation = 2.7%).

174
175 Depending on site and treatment, the ratio between factory dry mass and inventory dry mass varied
176 from 0.79 to 0.99 with an overall average at 0.85 - meaning that the field inventory overestimated
177 actual harvest by about 15%.

178
179 At the time of harvesting, researchers determined for each experimental block: productive time
180 consumption; delay time (Björheden et al. 1995); number of trips (for forwarders only); payload fill
181 rate (actual load as a % of maximum available payload volume – forwarders only); extraction
182 distance (forwarder only – estimated from Google Earth pictures, from the center of the
183 experimental block to the center of the landing). These figures were matched with the corrected
184 block mass estimated (bone-dry tons or BDT) in order to calculate machine productivity (BDT hour⁻¹
185) and payload size (BDT trip⁻¹, forwarders only).

186
187 As a safe measure, block-level time consumption was determined concurrently by the researchers
188 on site using stopwatches (Tag Heuer - 1 s accuracy) and by the operators on the machines using
189 their own wristwatches (obviously at a lower definition – 1 min accuracy). Furthermore, action
190 cameras (Apex cam) were attached to all machines, in order to acquire a permanent record of
191 operation in case of any doubts or mess-ups. All data used in the final block study derived from the
192 researcher time study and were quite accurate in both the timing itself and in the separation of

193 work time from delays (Bjorheden et al. 1995). For additional safeguard, researcher records and
194 operator records were compared and they all presented a reasonably good match, which excluded
195 any gross errors in time data collection.

196
197 Occasionally, the mass of wood on one block would exceed the capacity of the forwarder assigned
198 to that block. When that occurred, partial loads were hauled in order not to mix the time and the
199 materials belonging to each block. In that case, researchers would visually estimate payload fill rate
200 at 5% accuracy. Therefore, the vehicle travel time was multiplied by the payload fill rate of that load
201 in order to account for the fact that a full load would have been extracted in real operational
202 conditions, and therefore that same travel time would have been distributed over a larger payload.
203 For instance, if payload fill rate was 50%, then measured forwarder travel time would be multiplied
204 by 0.50 because under normal conditions that travel time would have been performed while
205 carrying a full load – not a half load. Therefore, when payload is divided by time in order to estimate
206 productivity, using a half payload without any corrections on the travel time would return an
207 unrealistically low productivity figure.

208
209 The study did not last long enough to produce a reliable estimate of delay time, which is typically
210 erratic. Therefore, all comparisons were conducted using the actual recorded figures of delay-free
211 productive work time per experimental block, after inflating it by 20% in order to account for
212 preparation and delays, as obtained from specific long-term scientific studies of delay time (Spinelli
213 and Visser 2008).

214
215 The block-level time study was supplemented with a parallel cycle-level study conducted on the
216 harvester. This was an elemental time study (Magagnotti et al. 2011), where researchers separately
217 recorded felling time, processing time, and biomass management time. In particular, felling time
218 began when the harvester head (and/or the machine) started moving towards the tree to be felled
219 and ended when the feed rollers started to turn; from there started processing time, which ended
220 when the last log was crosscut; biomass management time occupied the remaining productive work
221 time until the head (and/or the machine) started moving towards the next tree to be cut. The goal
222 of this study component was to check if any specific grading option would specifically impact one of
223 the work tasks. In particular, one wanted to determine if and how much processing time would
224 decrease as a result of renouncing the manufacture of a second log, or it would increase if SED would
225 be reduced to 7 cm over bark (and therefore the proportion of log material would expand). Similarly,
226 this study component would also help understanding if any increase/decrease in the time
227 consumption for one specific task would be offset by a proportional decrease/increase in the time
228 consumption for another complementary task in the same cycle. The time study was conducted for
229 most work cycles in the experiment, and namely: 5090 valid cycles. Each cycle corresponded to one
230 tree.

231
232 Machine rates were the prices actually charged by the service providers. These were: 40 € per
233 scheduled machine hour (SMH) for the Sampo forwarder; 55 € SMH⁻¹ for the Rottne forwarder; 65
234 € SMH⁻¹ for the Rottne harvester. The Authors acknowledge that local rates can hardly offer a
235 general benchmark and encourage readers operating under very different economic environments
236 to recalculate harvesting cost using their own rates and the productivity data presented in this
237 paper.

238
239 The block study data was used to quantify log yield, machine productivity and treatment cost
240 (dependent variables) as average values, and the differences between alternative treatments

241 (independent variables) was checked using the general linear model (GLM) technique, which was
242 both accurate and robust against violations of the main statistical assumptions. However, when the
243 visual inspection of residual plots showed that violations were strong, then non-parametric statistics
244 were deployed (Mann-Whitney unpaired comparison test). For all analyses, the significance level
245 was set at $\alpha < 0.05$. The analyses were implemented with the software Minitab 17, one of the most
246 popular statistical softwares in the field of engineering (Okagbue et al. 2021)

247

248

249 **Results**

250

251 The plantation in Nivky was better developed and had a significantly larger stocking (+16%) than
252 that in Gajary, due to higher site fertility and/or better clonal selection (Table 1).

253

254

255 *Insert TABLE 1 – Here*

256

257

258 Relative log yield as a % of the total harvest was clearly different between sites and treatments. Site
259 effect was best appreciated by comparing the data for the control blocks (treatment 0) in the two
260 different sites. If the same standard treatment was applied, log yield was 24% higher in the richer
261 site (Nivky), partly due to clonal differences. However, the allometric analyses confirmed that clonal
262 differences did not include form or branching, which were quite similar between clones. Statistical
263 analysis (GLM) also confirmed that the comparisons conducted at the two sites were each
264 performed under even conditions for both treatments on test, with no significant differences in the
265 mean values for surface area, DBH or stocking between experimental blocks assigned to different
266 treatments on the same site.

267

268 *Grading strategy effects*

269

270 Under the conditions encountered at the Nivky plantation, renouncing the production of a second
271 log incurred a 17% drop in log yield while accruing a 6% overall cost saving (Table 2). What is more,
272 the drop in log yield was highly significant, while the cost saving was not. Therefore, it may be stated
273 that this strategy produced significant log yield losses while failing to accrue any proportional cost
274 savings.

275

276 *Insert TABLE 2 – Here*

277

278

279 Under the conditions encountered at the Gajary plantation, reducing the small end diameter
280 specification from 8 cm to 7 cm accrued a 18% log yield increase at no significant cost increase – in
281 fact, total harvesting cost seemed to decrease by 6%, although this difference was not significant.
282 On the other hand, the log yield increase was highly significant.

283

284 In this case, the fact that cost decreased alongside SED specifications was associated with an
285 increase in forwarder productivity, since harvester productivity remained virtually unaltered. The
286 possible explanation was that a reduction of SED would also result in a proportional reduction of
287 the biomass fraction, which was forwarded with low efficiency due to its bulky nature. Biomass loads

288 were generally lighter than log loads and were much below the optimum forwarder payload. While
289 the results of this study were not conclusive in that regard, it is likely that a reduction of SED
290 specifications may favour a reduction of overall harvesting cost, rather than an increase.

291
292 The results of the time study indicated that the mean cycle time ranged from 24 to 27 s tree⁻¹, and
293 that processing (delimiting and crosscutting) time represented between 15 and 20% of total work
294 time (Figure 2). The analysis of variance showed that differences between treatments were
295 significant, especially for what concerned the “Simplified” treatment, which had the shortest
296 processing time, but also the longest felling time – likely to achieve a better felling angle for
297 managing the longer top resulting from this treatment. In general, most differences were
298 statistically significant, but that was likely the inevitable result of a very large dataset, with over
299 1000 observations per treatment. With such a large data set it was difficult not to pick up even small
300 differences, and indeed the differences were very small – in the order of few seconds. Therefore,
301 even if significant, such small differences would be obscured by larger variations in individual tree
302 characteristics, leading to an overall non-significance outcome at the larger block level.

303

304

305 *Insert FIGURE 2 – Here*

306

307

308 Most relevant to this specific test was the fact that logs produced under the reduced SED treatment
309 (7 cm) were indeed sent to the factory and fed to the production lines. Factory trials showed that 7
310 cm SED logs were acceptable and therefore the new specification could be introduced without any
311 negative consequences on factory processing.

312

313 *Operator effects*

314

315 The test in Gajary also allowed gauging operator effect, which was strong and highly significant
316 (Table 3). Operator Y was over 20% more productive than operator X, which resulted in a 20%
317 reduction of felling and processing cost (4 € BDT⁻¹ cheaper for Operator Y, compared with Operator
318 X). Furthermore, the forwarder achieved a higher productivity and incurred a lower cost when
319 dealing with the blocks harvested by Operator Y, although differences were not statistically
320 significant at the 5% level and therefore this result was considered suggestive rather than
321 conclusive. Eventually, total cost was significantly lower for the blocks harvested by operator Y, with
322 no differences between SED treatments. Better operator performance accrued savings for 6 € BDT⁻¹,
323 or almost 20% of the total. That was achieved under the same stand stocking conditions and with
324 no prejudice to log yield. In fact, Operator Y did not only achieve a higher productivity, but he may
325 have also reached better work quality standards, if forwarder performance could be indicative of
326 better stack management – which the data did not prove, but they did suggest.

327

328

329 *Insert TABLE 3 – Here*

330

331

332 The analysis of variance (ANOVA) associated with the GLM showed that operator effect dominated
333 over treatment effect (Table 4). In particular, stocking was not affected by treatment or operator,
334 which was consistent with a proper experimental design that avoided any site bias. Similarly, log
335 yield was only affected by treatment – which was further evidence of a good experimental design.

336 Operator effect was the main driver of differences in harvester performance and explained 80% of
337 its total variability, largely overcoming any background noise. Since the company, the machine and
338 the applied machine rate were the same, harvester cost showed an identical trend.

339
340

341 *Insert TABLE 4 – Here*

342
343

344 The cycle-level elemental time study showed that Operator Y took significantly less time to process
345 a tree and to manage the biomass residue derived from the processing (tops and branches),
346 regardless of treatment (Figure 3). The difference was especially meaningful for the biomass
347 management task, where it amounted to approximately 30%.

348
349

350 *Insert FIGURE 3 – Here*

351
352

353 The ANOVA conducted on the elemental time study data showed that both operator and SED
354 treatment effect were significant, but also that their strength was relatively small (< 1% of SS) –
355 especially for the SED treatment effect (Table 5).

356
357

358 *Insert TABLE 5 – Here*

359
360

361 In contrast, the results for the forwarder were inconclusive, although they suggested that a better
362 performance was achieved when dealing with the blocks treated by Operator Y. At any rate, the far
363 superior performance of Operator Y reflected on the total harvesting cost, which was significantly
364 lower for the blocks he treated. The ANOVA showed that this difference was clearly related to
365 operator effect, rather than SED treatment (Table 4).

366

367 Overall, the SED treatment only impacted log yield (as it was designed to do), while time
368 consumption, productivity and cost were impacted only by operator performance – not SED
369 treatment.

370

371 *Site/stocking effects*

372

373 Concerning the effect of site conditions on harvester productivity and cost, the comparison was
374 conducted between the Nivky and the Gajary sites, only for the control option (Treatment 0) and
375 for Operator X, who was the only one to have driven the Rottne H8 harvester at both sites (while
376 Operator Y only worked at Gajary, but not at Nivky). For that reason, the dataset presented a gross
377 unbalance, with 8 data points for Nivky, but only 4 for Gajary. Therefore, the comparison between
378 sites was conducted with the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test, which is designed to compare
379 two alternative treatments and can cope with dataset unbalance.

380

381 The analysis showed that there were significant differences between sites for both stocking and log
382 yield, which were 20% lower in Gajary – the less developed of the two plantations (Table 6). As a
383 consequence, harvester productivity was 15% lower in Gajary, and the difference was statistically

384 significant. Forwarder productivity was slightly higher in Gajary compared with Nivky, but the
385 forwarding comparison was biased by the use of two different forwarder models and forwarder
386 operators at the two sites, so it was impossible to determine whether the eventual differences
387 depended on site, machine or operator effects. In any case, the forwarder performance and cost
388 differences were not significant. Total harvesting cost was significantly higher for the less developed
389 site, as was expected. The cost increase amounted to 5.5 € BDT⁻¹ or 18%.

390

391

392

393

394 *Insert TABLE 6 – Here*

395

396

397 **Discussion**

398

399 First of all, one must address the main limitation of this study, which is that of focusing on one
400 specific stand type at a set moment in its development. The effects of simplifying tree processing or
401 reducing SED specifications are closely related to a specific tree size and product type. The very
402 same measures may have very different effects if trees were much larger (or smaller), or if
403 assortment length was set at 3 m instead of 4 m, for instance.

404

405 Before considering any of the measures presented in this paper, interested parties should first
406 match their own length specifications with the mensuration data for their plantations in order to
407 see how much the proposed measures would affect log yield – at least on paper.

408

409 This study only offers one example, which is practically relevant to medium-rotation poplar
410 plantations only. The experiment should be repeated whenever one would consider applying the
411 same principles to other species, rotations or product types. On the other hand, there are already
412 many thousands of hectares of these plantations in Eastern Europe, with a very large potential for
413 further expansion (Werner et al. 2012), and that likely guarantees some interest for the specific
414 results of this study.

415

416 Another important limitation of this study was with operator selection. Only one harvester operator
417 was tested in Nivky, while two harvester operators were tested in Gajary. Since the operator was
418 the same for both treatment on test, the comparison was indeed valid and there should be no issues
419 with that. However, one may wonder if the results of this (valid) comparison would not be affected
420 by the capacity of the individual operator to make the best of the innovation being tested. In other
421 words, one cannot exclude that the inconclusive results for Treatment A (simplified) would depend
422 on that specific operator being unable to fully exploit the potential of the innovative simplified
423 grading mode. This remains a possibility, although both the data and the visual observation of the
424 work process tend to confirm that this operator could have not done more than he did to reap all
425 the expected benefits of the new proposed grading method.

426

427 Further support to a cautious generalization of the results of this study across multiple operators is
428 the fact that in Gajary - where two operators were tested – operator effect proved to be dominant,
429 but treatment effect remained unchanged between operators. Therefore, both operators reacted
430 to treatment in the same way, even if they showed wide differences in individual performance. This
431 suggests that operators will be affected by treatment in the same way regardless of individual

432 proficiency levels, thus corroborating the assumption that the trends described in this study may
433 have general validity. Other studies have shown that specific harvesting method treatments would
434 affect operator performance with the same trends, independently of operator competence (Spinelli
435 et al. 2020). In this specific case, it is also worth stressing that the grading treatment would mostly
436 impact that one work task – processing – where operator experience and dexterity were the least
437 important, since performance of this task was largely automatic, especially when manufacturing
438 logs to a single length standard and with little or no limitations on defects. As a matter of fact, the
439 elemental time study showed that operator effect was most visible in such tasks as felling and
440 biomass management, both of which required extensive manoeuvring of the hydraulic loader and
441 required somewhat more work planning and dexterity than processing proper. Furthermore, the
442 overall incidence of the processing task was quite small, accounting for approximately 20% of the
443 total work cycle, which is consistent with the findings of other studies on small tree harvesting
444 (Nakagawa et al. 2007: processing = 16% of total cycle) and would dampen the impact on the total
445 cycle of any possible differences in processing time – if any actually existed.

447 The credibility of our results is backed by previous studies about the effect of operator variability
448 and the performance of CTL technology applied to small-sized hardwood trees. Concerning the
449 former, the 20% difference reported in this study falls very well within the 25%-50% range of
450 variation between the least and the most productive harvester operators indicated by previous
451 studies (Kirk et al. 1997; Leonello et al. 2012; Ovaskainen and Heikkila 2007; Purfürst and Erler 2011).
452 Less information is available on the performance of CTL technology when applied to medium-
453 rotation poplar, since most previous studies have been conducted using whole-tree harvesting
454 equipment (Spinelli and Hartsough 2006, Spinelli et al. 2021). The only recent paper on the subject
455 indicates a productivity around 4.5 BDT SMH⁻¹, achieved in a plantation that was almost identical to
456 that in Gajary (Magagnotti et al. 2021). That figure is 60% higher than recorded in this study, which
457 can be explained by the fact that a larger and faster machine was used, and that its operator was
458 the manufacturer's test driver, chosen among the best operators on the market to maximize the
459 impact of the eventual demonstration trials.

461 On those bases, we feel quite confident about the capacity of this study to offer reliable information
462 about the effect of alternative grading strategies. In particular, it seems safe to state that neither
463 process simplification (one log only) nor SED manipulation may have a large impact on harvester
464 productivity – at least within the approximate boundaries explored in this study. The only reference
465 specifically addressing the relationship between SED and harvester productivity agrees with our
466 conclusions (Holzleitner et al. 2019), and that for a larger change in the SED specification (from 8 to
467 4 cm, instead of from 8 to 7 cm). In that regard, it is also worth recalling that none of the currently
468 available harvester productivity models include SED or log number, but focus almost exclusively on
469 total stem volume (Nurminen et al. 2006, Spinelli et al 2010). In fact, some studies do report of a
470 significant effect of log number on productivity, but they refer to the number of log sorts rather than
471 to the number of logs of the same sort (Siren and Aaltio 2003, Tolan and Visser 2015). It is indeed
472 reasonable to expect that adding one log to the tree harvesting process may have little effect on
473 productivity, given that most of the work cycle time is spent reaching for the tree, grabbing it and
474 laying it down horizontal ready for processing. Once cut and in the harvester head's grasp, the tree
475 is relatively easy to handle: manufacturing one additional log only takes pushing a button and
476 waiting very few seconds. When processing poplars, tree form may have a stronger effect than just
477 the number of logs, and for that reason a form index has been included in some of the existing
478 harvester productivity models (Puttock et al. 2005): however, the treatments tested in this study
479 were not associated with tree form, nor would one expect much of a form variability in an even-

480 aged clonal plantation. In fact, statistical analysis of the form factors determined for the two clones
481 through destructive sampling confirmed the absence of any form differences between the two
482 clones used in this experiment.

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484 Concerning the effect of alternative grading strategies on log yield, logics are more persuasive than
485 any corroborating studies – even though the latter are also available. These have shown that
486 increasing SED from 6 cm to 9 cm may result in log yield dropping by approximately 50% (Pasanen
487 et al 2014), even though it may be difficult to accurately predict the effect of SED changes on tree
488 mass distribution when dealing with small trees (Räisänen and Nurmi 2011). More in general,
489 excessive SED specifications are among the main causes for poor value recovery in small-tree
490 operations (Boston and Murphy 2003), which ultimately supports the decision to reduce SED from
491 8 cm to 7 cm. Considering that these studies deal with different tree species (softwood) and
492 silvicultural treatments (thinning), the fact that our figures fall well within their ballpark may be
493 taken as sufficient validation.

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496 **Conclusions**

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498 Grading strategies aimed at simplifying and speeding CTL harvester work do not seem to produce
499 much benefit: their effect on productivity is negligible, while there is a risk of negatively affecting
500 log yield. Conversely, relaxing SED specifications may significantly boost log yield at no additional
501 cost. In fact, a reduction in SED specification may help offsetting the log yield and productivity losses
502 associated with decreasing stand stocking, at least to a certain extent. In any case, if the factory can
503 handle such small logs, it pays to reduce SED from 8 cm to 7 cm. The study also offered ideal
504 conditions for probing operator effect and showed that productivity differences between operators
505 may account for a 20% variation in harvesting productivity and cost – which is as large or larger than
506 the grading treatment effect. Therefore, much attention should be devoted to operator selection,
507 training and motivation, as already advocated by human factors specialists (Schwegman et al. 2021).

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Table 1 – Characteristics of the experimental blocks (mean values)

Site		Nivky	Nivky	Gajary	Gajary
Treatment	Code	0	A	0	B
Treatment	Description	Control	Simplified	Control	Reduced
Observations	n° blocks	8	8	8	8
Block surface area	ha	0.101 ^a	0.098 ^a	0.095 ^a	0.093 ^a
DBH	cm	12.2 ^a	12.4 ^a	11.9 ^a	11.7 ^a
Height	m	15.1 ^a	15.1 ^a	14.9 ^b	14.9 ^b
Block mass	BDT	5.26 ^a	5.20 ^a	4.28 ^b	4.15 ^b
Stocking	BDT ha-1	52.4 ^a	53 ^a	45.1 ^b	44.7 ^b
Log yield	%	60.8 ^a	50.4 ^b	49.2 ^b	58.6 ^a

647 Notes: DBH = Diameter at breast height, BDT = Bone-Dry tons (0% water mass fraction); different
 648 superscript letters on mean values on the same row indicate a statistically significant difference at the 5% level.
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Table 2 – Comparison between different grading options

Test in Nivky - Effect of simplified grading (Treatment A)				
Treatment	Code	0	A	Significance
Treatment	Description	Control	Simplified	p-Value
Observations	n° blocks	8	8	
Stocking	BDT ha ⁻¹	52.4	53.1	0.6434
Log yield	%	61	50	0.0012
Harvester productivity	BDT SMH ⁻¹	3.2	3.5	0.1052
Harvester cost	€ BDT ⁻¹	20.3	18.9	0.1052
Forwarder productivity	BDT SMH ⁻¹	4.2	4.4	0.1052
Forwarder cost	€ BDT ⁻¹	9.6	9.1	0.1052
Total harvesting cost	€ BDT ⁻¹	29.9	28.0	0.0641
Test in Gajary - Effect of reduced SED specification (Treatment B)				
Treatment	Code	0	B	Significance
Treatment	Description	Control	Reduced	p-Value
Observations	n° blocks	8	8	
Stocking	BDT ha ⁻¹	45.1	44.7	0.8336
Log yield	%	49	58	0.0023
Harvester productivity	BDT SMH ⁻¹	3.1	3.2	0.5995
Harvester cost	€ BDT ⁻¹	21.2	20.6	0.5995
Forwarder productivity	BDT SMH ⁻¹	5.3	6.1	0.0929
Forwarder cost	€ BDT ⁻¹	11.1	9.8	0.0929
Total harvesting cost	€ BDT ⁻¹	32.3	30.4	0.2936

658 Notes: BDT = Bone-Dry tons (0% water mass fraction); SMH = Scheduled Machine Hour, including delays.

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Table 3 – Operator comparison conducted at the Gajary site

Operator		X	Y	X	Y
Treatment	Code	0	0	B	B
Treatment	Description	Control	Control	Reduced	Reduced
Observations	n° blocks	4	4	4	4
SED	cm	8	8	7	7
Stocking	BDT ha ⁻¹	43.7 ^a	46.5 ^a	43.3 ^a	46.1 ^a
Log yield	%	47.6 ^a	50.8 ^a	57.0 ^b	60.1 ^b
Harvester productivity	BDT SMH ⁻¹	2.8 ^a	3.4 ^b	2.9 ^a	3.6 ^b
Harvester cost	€ BDT ⁻¹	23.3 ^a	19.0 ^b	22.8 ^a	18.4 ^b
Forwarder productivity	BDT SMH ⁻¹	4.6 ^a	5.9 ^a	5.1 ^a	7.2 ^a
Forwarder cost	€ BDT ⁻¹	12.1 ^a	10.1 ^a	10.9 ^a	8.7 ^a
Total harvesting cost	€ BDT ⁻¹	35.4 ^a	29.1 ^b	33.7 ^a	27.1 ^b

670 Notes: SED = Small-end diameter, over bark; BDT = Bone-Dry tons (0% water mass fraction); SMH = Scheduled Machine
671 Hour, including delays; different superscript letters on mean values on the same row indicate a statistically significant
672 difference at the 5% level.

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Table 4 – Results from the ANOVA (GLM) conducted on the data collected in Gajary

Dependent variable	Effect	DF	SS	η^2	F-Value	P-Value
Stocking BDT ha ⁻¹	SED	1	0.671	0.00	0.048	0.8301
	Operator	1	30.784	0.15	2.206	0.1633
	Interaction	1	0.010	0.00	0.001	0.9796
	Residual	12	167.479	0.84		
Log Yield %	SED	1	349.731	0.62	24.26	0.0004
	Operator	1	41.516	0.07	2.880	0.1155
	Interaction	1	0.010	0.00	0.001	0.9796
	Residual	12	172.988	0.31		
Harvester Productivity BDT SMH ⁻¹	SED	1	0.028	0.01	0.785	0.3930
	Operator	1	1.844	0.80	50.89	<0.0001
	Interaction	1	0.002	0.00	0.050	0.8271
	Residual	12	0.435	0.19		
Harvester Cost € BDT ⁻¹	SED	1	1.296	0.01	1.090	0.3170
	Operator	1	77.668	0.83	65.326	<0.0001
	Interaction	1	0.008	0.00	0.007	0.9355
	Residual	12	14.267	0.15		
Forwarder Productivity BDT SMH ⁻¹	SED	1	3.066	0.05	0.723	0.4119
	Operator	1	11.882	0.18	2.801	0.1201
	Interaction	1	0.737	0.01	0.174	0.6841
	Residual	12	50.911	0.76		
Forwarder Cost € BDT ⁻¹	SED	1	6.694	0.07	1.202	0.2945
	Operator	1	16.787	0.19	3.014	0.1082
	Interaction	1	0.059	0.00	0.011	0.9196
	Residual	12	66.844	0.74		
Total cost Cost € BDT ⁻¹	SED	1	13.881	0.05	1.387	0.2618
	Operator	1	166.67	0.55	16.651	0.0015
	Interaction	1	0.111	0.00	0.011	0.9178
	Residual	12	120.116	0.40		

679 Notes: SED = Small-end diameter, over bark; BDT = Bone-Dry tons (0% water mass fraction); SMH = Scheduled Machine
680 Hour, including delays; SED = small end diameter; DF = Degrees of Freedom; SS = Sum of Squares; η^2 = strength of effect
681 (SS for the effect/Total SS); n = 16.

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Table 5 – Results from the ANOVA (GLM) conducted on the elemental time study data

Dependent variable	Effect	DF	SS	η^2	F-Value	P-Value
Felling time s tree ⁻¹	SED	1	34.3	0.000	1.099	0.2945
	Operator	1	76.0	0.001	2.433	0.1190
	Interaction	1	1273.4	0.016	40.755	<0.0001
	Residual	2536	79240.9	0.983		
Processing time s tree ⁻¹	SED	1	100.3	0.003	8.524	0.0035
	Operator	1	121.7	0.004	10.338	0.0013
	Interaction	1	17.5	0.001	1.485	0.2231
	Residual	2536	29853.4	0.992		
Biomass management Time s tree ⁻¹	SED	1	342.8	0.006	19.337	<0.0001
	Operator	1	9429.7	0.172	531.963	<0.0001
	Interaction	1	139.6	0.003	7.873	0.0051
	Residual	2536	44953.9	0.819		

692 Notes: SED = small end diameter over bark; DF = Degrees of Freedom; SS = Sum of Squares;
 693 η^2 = strength of effect (SS for the effect/Total SS); n = 2540

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Table 6 – Comparison between different sites for the same standard grading option (control)

Site		Nivky	Gajary	Significance
Treatment	Code	0	0	p-Value
Treatment	Description	Control	Control	
Observations	n° blocks	8	4	
SED	cm	8	8	
Stocking	BDT ha ⁻¹	52.4	43.7	0.0066
Log yield	%	60.8	47.6	0.0066
Harvester productivity	BDT SMH ⁻¹	3.2	2.8	0.0066
Harvester cost	€ BDT ⁻¹	20.3	23.3	0.0066
Forwarder productivity	BDT SMH ⁻¹	4.2	4.6	0.1264
Forwarder cost	€ BDT ⁻¹	9.6	12.1	0.1264
Total harvesting cost	€ BDT ⁻¹	29.9	35.4	0.0066

703 Notes: SED = Small-end diameter, over bark; BDT = Bone-Dry tons (0% water mass fraction); SMH = Scheduled Machine
 704 Hour, including delays; SED = small end diameter. P-Value according to the Mann-Whitney non-parametric test.
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Figure 1 – The machines used in test: Rottne H8 (top); Rottne F10 (centre); Sampo FR28 (bottom)

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Figure 2 – Harvester cycle time: task breakdown (mean values) by site and treatment

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Figure 3 – Harvester cycle time in Gajary: task breakdown (mean values) by treatment and operator

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